

Data management plan of the INNOVA project

Version 0

Description

The INNOVA project aims to develop an innovative solution for the operational management of a low-inertia, weakly interconnected power system with a high share of renewables to foster energy supply stability, reliability and cost-efficiency. This document outlines the principles for research data management and sharing of project's scientific outputs and findings. DMP is continuously updated during the project's duration (2024-2026).

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Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data management plan of the INNOVA project](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [No. lzp-2023/1-0376](#)

Project: [Innovative emergency control of RESdominated low-inertia power systems \(INNOVA\)](#)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Cost-benefit assessment of the INNOVA solution: input data and results

This is a preliminary template describing a dataset to be prepared during the INNOVA project. The dataset is going to comprise the input data used and results of the economic assessment of the INNOVA control scheme based on market modelling of power system future scenarios.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data has been collected and generated to perform and present the economic assessment of the INNOVA control scheme based on market modelling of power system future scenarios.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Other

Tabular data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Although part of the data might be reused from existing open access models and studies, majority of the data will be generated through modelling efforts during the INNOVA project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Research community, e.g. energy and power system modellers; students; energy sector stakeholders; policy makers.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

There is no single metadata standard for power system and electricity market modelling. Existing standardisation efforts and initiatives will be further explored during the project to potentially select a suitable metadata standard for INNOVA modelling data.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Basic spreadsheet software.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV is a common data exchange format for tabular data widely supported by various spreadsheet and database programs as well as data science tools.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The most prevalent community-approved, attribution-based data-capable open license. Mandatory attribution can contribute to provenance tracking.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2036-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Within the project budget.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Zane Broka (orcid:0000-0002-7082-7332)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Security measures applied according to the data repository policies.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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